

APPENDIX

A. Coefficient Matrices and Vectors in Illustrative Case

$$\mathbf{H} = \begin{bmatrix} 1.86 & 0 & 0 \\ -1.17 & 1.86 & 0 \\ 0 & -1.17 & 1.86 \\ -1.86 & 0 & 0 \\ 1.17 & -1.86 & 0 \\ 0 & 1.17 & -1.86 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{h} = \begin{bmatrix} 41.45 \\ 16.73 \\ 15.51 \\ -35.45 \\ 10.73 \\ 9.51 \\ -19 \\ -19 \\ 23 \\ 23 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{H}^{base} = \begin{bmatrix} 81.33 & 0 & 0 \\ -51.25 & 14.66 & 0 \\ 0 & -9.24 & 27.65 \\ -81.33 & 0 & 0 \\ 51.25 & -14.66 & 0 \\ 0 & 9.24 & -27.65 \\ 0 & -7.88 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -14.87 \\ 0 & 7.88 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 14.87 \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{h}^{base} = \begin{bmatrix} 1812.82 \\ -804.03 \\ 384.98 \\ -1791.73 \\ 826.42 \\ -363.01 \\ -167.46 \\ -306.67 \\ 180.32 \\ 323.05 \end{bmatrix}$$

B. Detailed Removing Process for AC Sets

First, the thermal dynamic equations in (2.c) can be recast as below:

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c1} \mathbf{T}_{i,k}^m + \mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c2} \mathbf{T}_{i,k}^a + \mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c3} \mathbf{P}_{i,k} = \mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c4} \\ \mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c5} \mathbf{T}_{i,k}^m + \mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c6} \mathbf{T}_{i,k}^a + \mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c7} \mathbf{P}_{i,k} = \mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c8} \end{cases} \quad (30.a)$$

where $\mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{[.]}$ is the compact coefficient matrix. Since $\mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c1}$, $\mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c2}$, $\mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c5}$, and $\mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c6}$ are invertible matrix, we recast the constraint on the upper and lower limits of indoor temperature as follows.

$$\mathbf{T}_{i,k}^{set} - \beta_{i,k}^{set} \leq \mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c10} - \mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c9} \mathbf{P}_{i,k} \leq \mathbf{T}_{i,k}^{set} + \beta_{i,k}^{set} \quad (30.b)$$

where

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c9} = \mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c11} \left(\mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c7} - \mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c5} \left(\mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c1} \right)^{-1} \mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c3} \right) \\ \mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c10} = \mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c11} \left(\mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c8} - \mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c5} \left(\mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c1} \right)^{-1} \mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c4} \right) \\ \mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c11} = \left(\mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c6} - \mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c5} \left(\mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c1} \right)^{-1} \mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c2} \right)^{-1} \end{cases} \quad (30.c)$$

Thus, we obtain the equivalent flexibility set of the individual AC in power space as below:

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{T}_{i,k}^{set} - \beta_{i,k}^{set} \leq \mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c10} - \mathbf{A}_{i,k}^{c9} \mathbf{P}_{i,k} \leq \mathbf{T}_{i,k}^{set} + \beta_{i,k}^{set} \\ \mathbf{P}_{i,k}^{\min} \leq \mathbf{P}_{i,k} \leq \mathbf{P}_{i,k}^{\max} \end{cases} \quad (30.d)$$

Further, we can recast (30.d) as a compact H-representation form to derive the coefficient matrices in (18).

C. Proof of Containment Constraint Reformulation

Given a base set as shown in (19), $\mathbb{U}_{i,k}^{aff}$ can be expressed as:

$$\mathbb{U}_{i,k}^{aff} = \left\{ \mathbf{P}_{i,k}^{aff} = \mathbf{\Gamma}_{i,k}^{aff} \mathbf{P}_{i,k}^a + \boldsymbol{\gamma}_{i,k}^{aff}, \forall \mathbf{H}_i^{base,proj} \mathbf{P}_{i,k}^a \leq \mathbf{h}_i^{base,proj} \right\} \quad (31.a)$$

Also, $\mathbb{U}_{i,k}^{aff}$ can be expressed in a H-representation form:

$$\mathbb{U}_{i,k}^{aff} = \left\{ \mathbf{H}_{i,k}^{aff,proj} \mathbf{P}_{i,k}^{aff} \leq \mathbf{h}_{i,k}^{aff,proj} \right\} \quad (31.b)$$

where $\mathbf{H}_{i,k}^{aff,proj}$ and $\mathbf{h}_{i,k}^{aff,proj}$ are coefficient matrices.

Combining (31.a) and (31.b), we can derive (31.c):

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{H}_{i,k}^{aff,proj} \mathbf{\Gamma}_{i,k}^{aff} = \mathbf{H}_i^{base,proj} \\ \mathbf{h}_{i,k}^{aff,proj} = \mathbf{h}_i^{base,proj} + \mathbf{H}_{i,k}^{aff,proj} \boldsymbol{\gamma}_{i,k}^{aff} \end{cases} \quad (31.c)$$

According to [31], the containment constraint $\mathbb{U}_{i,k}^{aff} \subseteq \mathbb{U}_{i,k}$ can be expressed as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{A}_{i,k} \geq 0 \\ \mathbf{A}_{i,k} \mathbf{H}_{i,k}^{aff,proj} = \mathbf{H}_{i,k}^{proj} \\ \mathbf{A}_{i,k} \mathbf{h}_{i,k}^{aff,proj} \leq \mathbf{h}_{i,k}^{proj} \end{cases} \quad (31.d)$$

where $\mathbf{A}_{i,k}$ is the auxiliary variable matrix.

Combining (31.c) and (31.d), we can derive (21.a)-(21.c). ■